

EFFECTS OF SLIT ANGLE OF UNIDIRECTIONALLY ARRAYED CHOPPED STRANDS (UACS) ON THE THERMAL RESIDUAL STRESS IN UACS/AL LAMINATE

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1 General Introduction

Fiber reinforced composites have been widely used in the many industries such as aircraft, aerospace, automobiles, ships, wind turbine blades, and civil constructions. In the recent years, among the families of fiber-reinforced composites, a relatively new family named as fiber metal laminates (FMLs) or fiber-reinforced metal laminates (FRMLs) have attracted considerable attentions. FMLs are a kind of metal-like hybrid composite materials consisting of metal sheets bonded to fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) layers. This kind of hybrid composite materials has been studied at Delft University of Technology since the late 1970's. Aramid fiber reinforced plastics/aluminum alloy (AFRP/Al), called as ARALL, and glass fiber reinforced plastic/aluminum alloy (GFRP/Al), called as GLARE, have been successfully developed at Delft University of Technology and the GLARE has been used in A380 as a new structural material.

In the early stage of the study of FMLs, CFRP was also considered as a potential composite layers combined with aluminum alloy to fabricate CARALL, since the CFRP has more advantages than AFRP and GFRP, such as higher specific stiffness and specific strength. Many researchers have made a lot of effort to develop CFRP/Al laminate over the last decades. However, up-to-date two major problems to the development of CFRP/Al laminate are still unsolved yet. The first is the galvanic corrosion problem due to the difference of natural potential between carbon and aluminum alloy. The galvanic corrosion may seriously reduce

the strength of aluminum during the serving period if a valid protection is not provided for aluminum alloy. The prevention of galvanic corrosion to aluminum layers of CFRP/Al laminate has been studied previously in, according to which a surface treatment method based on a sulfuric acid anodizing and a silica nano-particle reinforced hybrid sol-gel coating shows excellent corrosion resistance[1].

The second problem is the high thermal residual stresses in CFRP/Al laminate due to the large mismatch of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between CFRP and aluminum alloy. High thermal residual stresses lead to low fatigue strength of CFRP/Al laminate.

Recently, a lot of researches of unidirectionally arrayed chopped strands (UACS) have been conducted. UACS is made by introducing slits into a unidirectional prepreg, which allow the fiber strands to flow smoothly during molding. Therefore, it can be used to fabricate structure with complex shape, such as rib structure. When compared with traditional CFRP with continuous fibers, UACS has not only the advantage of better flowability but also the disadvantage of relatively lower tensile strength[2].

So far, no report has been published openly about the CFRP/Al made with UACS. This paper experimentally study the thermal residual stress of CARALL fabricated with UACS with different slit angles. It is speculated that the heating process in autoclave with 0.3MPa air pressure, slits expand and filled with resin, which will increase the thermal contraction of CFRP during cooling process.

2 Experiments

2.1 Materials

PYROFIL#350(TR50S) (Mitsubishi Rayon) are used in present experimental research strength of unidirectional PYROFIL#350(TR50S) is 2950MPa thickness of 0.2mm. Commercial 2024-T3 aluminum alloy sheet of 0.5mm in thickness is used as aluminum layer. The Young's modulus of the CFRP prepreg in fiber direction T2024-T3 is 142GPa and 71GPa respectively. The CTE of aluminum is $23 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. The CTE of CFRP in fiber direction is too small in value compared with the CTE of aluminum, therefore is assumed to be zero for the sake of simplicity in the theoretical calculation of thermal residual stress. The CTE of CFRP perpendicular to the fiber direction is almost the same as that of aluminum. Therefore, only the thermal residual stress in the fiber direction is investigated. Before fabrication, surface treatment based on a sulfuric acid anodizing and a silica nanoparticle reinforced hybrid sol-gel coating is conducted for 2024-T3 sheet to protect 2024-T3 sheet from galvanic corrosion and to improve the adhesive strength between CFRP layer and Al sheet. In the following sections, the 2024-T3 sheet means the surface treated 2024-T3 sheet for the sake of simplicity.

2.2 Fabrication

UACS, which is made by cutting parallel slits on unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg. Six cases are prepared with different slit angle θ , which is the angle between slit and fiber direction, including 5.7° ($\arctan 2.5/25$), 11.3° ($\arctan 5/25$), 16.7° ($\arctan 7.5/25$), 31° ($\arctan 15/25=31$), 45° and 90° . CFRP prepreg cut with slit angle of 11.3° , also known as UACS in this paper is shown in Fig.1. The distance between neighboring slits in fiber direction is 25mm in all cases.

Four pieces of prepreg ($150 \times 150 \times 0.2\text{mm}$) with alternate slit angle [$\theta/-\theta/\theta/-\theta$] are stacked together in the same fiber direction with two aluminum layers ($150 \times 150 \times 0.5\text{mm}$) on each side, and then fabricated using curing cycle recommended by the manufacturer of carbon fiber prepreg shown in Fig.2.

2.3 Tensile Test

The tensile specimen is 150mm in length, 12.7mm in width, and 1.8mm in thickness. Tensile tests are

conducted using a MTS 810 material-testing system with the crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min.

The tensile specimen is cut from the fabricated UACS/Al laminate using a diamond saw and its geometry is 150mm in length, 12.7mm in width, and 1.8mm in thickness shown in Fig.3. Aluminum tab of 40mm in length and 1mm in thickness is bonded at two ends of the specimen.

Tensile tests are conducted using a MTS 810 material-testing system with the crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min.

Since aluminum alloy is the only constituent that shows the yielding phenomenon in UACS/Al laminate, the deviation from linearity in the tensile stress-strain curve of UACS/Al laminate must be due to the yielding of the aluminum layer [3]. Thermal residual strain existing in the aluminum layer may shift the yield point of the UACS/Al laminate. The yield point is defined as the point of intersection of two tangent lines on the stress-strain curve as shown in Fig.4.

Hence, the residual strain in the aluminum layer of a UACS/Al laminate can be determined from the difference between the yield strain of the UACS/Al laminate and that of the unreinforced aluminum sheet as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{r,a} = \varepsilon_{y,a} - \varepsilon_{y,c} \quad (1)$$

where $\varepsilon_{y,a}$ and $\varepsilon_{y,c}$ is the yield strain of the aluminum alloy and UACS/Al laminate, and $\varepsilon_{r,a}$ is the thermal residual strain in aluminum layers of UACS/Al laminate. Then the thermal residual stress in aluminum layer of UACS/Al laminate can be approximately determined by:

$$\sigma_a = E_a \varepsilon_{r,a} \quad (2)$$

2.4 Classic laminate theory

For the sake of comparison with experimental results of thermal residual stress in fabricated CFRP/Al laminates, the thermal residual stress in fiber direction in fabricated CFRP/Al laminates is evaluated based on classic laminate theory.

Firstly, the force equilibrium equation in the fiber direction for the CARALL is expressed by

$$A_a \sigma_a + A_c \sigma_c = 0 \quad (3)$$

where A_a and A_c represent the cross-sectional areas of aluminum and CFRP layers, while σ_a and σ_c represent the stresses in the aluminum layer and CFRP layer in the fiber direction, respectively. Next, the condition of equal strain of the two materials is expressed by

$$\frac{\sigma_a}{E_a} + \alpha_a \Delta T = \frac{\sigma_c}{E_c} + \alpha_c \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where α_a and α_c represent the CTEs of aluminum and CFRP in the fiber direction, respectively, ΔT denotes the temperature difference between actual bonding temperature and room temperature. E_a and E_c denote the Young's modulus of aluminum and CFRP in fiber direction, respectively. Then, from Eq. (3) and Eq. (4), the thermal residual stresses in the aluminum and the CFRP layers can be expressed by

$$\sigma_a = (\alpha_a - \alpha_c) \Delta T \frac{E_c E_a A_c}{E_c A_c + E_a A_a} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\sigma_c = -(\alpha_a - \alpha_c) \Delta T \frac{E_c E_a A_a}{E_c A_c + E_a A_a} \quad (6)$$

respectively.

In the case of cure cycle recommended by manufacturer, the curing temperature is 127°C, and the room temperature is 25°C, then ΔT is 102°C. Considering unit width leads to $A_c=0.8\text{mm}^2$, $A_a=1\text{mm}^2$. Then inserting the Young's modulus values of 2024-T3 and CFRP in fiber direction, $\alpha_a=23 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, and $\alpha_c=0$ into above Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) lead to $\sigma_a = 102.5\text{MPa}$ and $\sigma_c = -128.1\text{MPa}$ for conventional CFRP/Al laminate with continuous fibers

3 Results and Discussion

Thermal residual stress in aluminum layers of conventional CFRP/Al laminate obtained by using yielding point shift method is 107MPa, which is in good agreement with the calculation results using classic laminate theory.

Fig.5 shows the cross-section view of UACS/Al specimen with slit angle of 16.7° after fracture. Aluminum layers are totally separated from UACS layers because of large plastic deformation, and therefore not shown in this figure. It is very obvious that slit cracks and delamination of the interfaces

occur in all four layers of UACS. No fiber breakage is observed, and delamination is the only failure mode in all cases.

The values obtained by tensile tests of UACS/Al laminate shown in Fig.6 are the average of at least three test specimens and the error bars for each value indicate the upper and lower limits of the measured results.

In Fig.6 it is shown that small slit angel lead to large tensile strength as expected, since smaller slit angle means lager axial stress along fiber direction and smaller shear stress which contribute to delamination.

Also shown in Fig.6, thermal residual stress is not consistent with slit angles. Thermal residual stress is relatively large in both cases of small slit angle, such as 5.7° and large slit angle, such as 45° and 90°. Specimen with slit angles between 11.3° and 31° has relatively low thermal residual stress. Among all the cases, specimen with slit angle of 11.3° is the most impressive one with relatively high tensile strength and largest reduction of thermal residual stress of 36.5% compared with CFRP/Al laminate fabricated using traditional CFRP.

4 Summary and conclusions

Following conclusions can be drawn from these experiment results:

1. Specimen with smaller slit angles have relative higher tensile strength;
2. Thermal residual stress is relatively large in both cases of small slit angle and large slit angle. Specimen with slit angles between 11.3° and 31° has relatively low thermal residual stress;
3. Delamination is the only failure mode in all cases, there are no fiber breakage observed.

Numerical analysis of the slit Effects of slit angle of unidirectionally arrayed chopped strands (UACS) on the thermal residual stress in UACS/Al laminate will be conducted in future research.

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Fig.1.UACS with slit angle of 11.3°

Fig.2 Cure cycle recommended by the manufacture of CFRP prepreg

Fig.3 Dimension of coupon specimen for tensile test

Fig.4 Illustration of yielding point shift method

Fig.5 Cross-section view of UACS/Al specimen after fracture

Fig.6 Tensile strength and thermal residual stress of UACS/Al laminates with different slit angles